

Fingolimod (FTY720) induces nitric oxide-dependent relaxation in the rat inferior vena cava via S1P₃ receptor activation

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Abstract

Background: Sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) regulates vascular tone through multiple receptor subtypes. Although fingolimod (FTY720) has well-established effects in arterial systems, its effects on venous function remain poorly characterized.

Objective: This study aimed to investigate the direct effects of FTY720 on venous tone, with particular emphasis on vasorelaxation in the rat inferior vena cava, and to determine the involvement of S1P₃ receptor-mediated nitric oxide (NO) signaling.

Methods: Isolated endothelium-intact rat inferior vena cava rings were mounted in organ baths for isometric tension recording. Vessels were precontracted with endothelin-1 (1 nM), followed by cumulative administration of FTY720 (1–30 μM). Mechanistic pathways were assessed using L-NAME, ODQ, and the S1P₃ antagonist CAY10444.

Results: FTY720 induced concentration-dependent relaxation (E_{max} 63.9 ± 5.1%, $p < 0.001$). Inhibition of nitric oxide synthase and soluble guanylate cyclase significantly reduced relaxation, indicating involvement of the NO–cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) pathway. S1P₃ receptor blockade nearly abolished the response, confirming receptor-specific signaling.

Conclusion: FTY720 induces significant venorelaxation and modulates venous tone in the rat inferior vena cava through an S1P₃-dependent mechanism involving NO and cGMP signaling. These findings extend the vascular profile of FTY720 to the venous system, highlighting a key pathway in regulating venous tone.

Graphical abstract

Keywords

FTY720, inferior vena cava, nitric oxide, sphingosine-1-phosphate, venorelaxation

Introduction

Sphingolipids are bioactive lipids that regulate a wide range of cellular processes, including vascular tone, endothelial function, inflammation, apoptosis, and angiogenesis. Within the cardiovascular system, sphingolipid signaling has emerged as a key regulator of endothelial integrity and vascular homeostasis (Weigel et al. 2023). Specifically, sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) exerts its biological effects through five G protein-coupled receptors (S1P₁–S1P₅), which are differentially expressed in endothelial and smooth muscle cells across vascular beds, including large arteries, resistance vessels, and veins. This spatial and cellular heterogeneity determines vessel-specific responses to S1P signaling (Cantalupo et al. 2017).

Importantly, activation of endothelial S1P₁ and S1P₃ receptors stimulates the PI3K/Akt pathway, leading to the phosphorylation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) and an increase in nitric oxide (NO) production. This promotes vasodilation, whereas S1P₂ and S1P₃ receptor signaling in smooth muscle promotes vasoconstriction (Tölle et al. 2005; Weigel et al. 2023). Accordingly, vascular tone is regulated by the dynamic balance between endothelium-derived relaxation and smooth muscle-mediated contraction, as demonstrated in vascular endothelial models and isolated vessel studies (Vanhoutte et al. 2017).

Fingolimod (FTY720) is a functional S1P receptor modulator widely used in multiple sclerosis (Volpi et al. 2019). Through modulation of S1P receptor subtypes, FTY720 exerts complex and context-dependent vascular effects, including both vasodilatory and vasoconstrictive responses, depending on receptor distribution and experimental conditions (Spijkers et al. 2012). In parallel, endothelial studies demonstrate that S1P receptor modulation

affects endothelial barrier function and NO-related signaling, supporting its contribution to vascular regulation (Weigel et al. 2023).

Experimental studies have shown that FTY720 modulates heart rate, vascular tone, and endothelial function. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies indicate bidirectional vascular effects, including endothelium-dependent vasodilation and smooth muscle-mediated vasoconstriction (Spijkers et al. 2012). In addition, chronic exposure has been associated with altered vascular reactivity, likely reflecting receptor desensitization and adaptive changes in endothelial signaling pathways (Shishavan et al. 2016). Clinical evidence also supports the vascular effects of FTY720 in humans, including altered endothelial function and vascular tone (Westhoff et al. 2007).

Importantly, beyond its established effects in arterial systems, emerging evidence indicates that S1P signaling also plays a vessel-specific role in the venous system. S1P₁ signaling has been implicated in the regulation of endothelial barrier integrity and venous endothelial function, with disruption of this pathway leading to abnormalities in venous vascular structure and function (Tobia et al. 2012). This preferential role of S1P signaling in the venous endothelium highlights the need for direct investigation of venous physiology, as regulatory mechanisms in capacitance vessels differ fundamentally from those in arterial circulation.

Collectively, these findings provide a mechanistic basis linking FTY720 to potential effects in the venous circulation. However, despite this biological plausibility, direct experimental evidence evaluating the effects of FTY720 on venous tone remains limited. The existing body of research is predominantly focused on arterial systems, resulting in a significant gap in understanding venous vascular pharmacology. This knowledge gap is particularly

important because veins, especially large capacitance vessels such as the inferior vena cava (IVC), play a central role in regulating venous return, cardiac preload, and overall cardiovascular homeostasis, and even small changes in venous tone can markedly influence cardiac output and systemic hemodynamics, underscoring the physiological and translational importance of studying venous reactivity (Rothe 1986; Gelman 2008). Therefore, it was hypothesized that FTY720 would modulate venous tone in the rat IVC via an endothelium-dependent, NO-mediated mechanism involving specific S1P receptors. The present study aimed to investigate the direct pharmacological effects of FTY720 on venous vascular tone using isolated rat IVC preparations and to elucidate the underlying mechanisms, with particular emphasis on endothelial NO-dependent pathways and S1P receptor-mediated signaling.

Materials and methods

Study design, setting, and ethical approval

This study was designed as an experimental *in vitro* investigation to evaluate the effects of FTY720 on venous vascular tone using isolated IVC segments from laboratory rats. All experiments were performed under standard laboratory conditions and in accordance with good laboratory practice (GLP) principles. All experimental procedures involving animals complied with international guidelines for animal research and relevant institutional ethical standards. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, University of Prishtina (Approval No. 6804). All efforts were made to minimize animal suffering and reduce the number of animals used throughout the study.

Experimental animals and housing conditions

Eighteen adult male Wistar rats (156–230 g) were used. The sample size was based on previous similar organ bath studies, and a total of 2–3 vessel rings were used per experimental group. Multiple vessel rings were obtained from individual animals and distributed across different experimental conditions (e.g., control and inhibitor groups) to minimize interanimal variability. The number of experimental replicates (*n*) refers to vessel preparations and is indicated in the corresponding figure legends. Animals were housed in standard ventilated cages (DGM™ ventilated animal research cages, Tecniplast, Buguggiate, Italy) under controlled environmental conditions (temperature 22 ± 2 °C, relative humidity $50 \pm 10\%$, 12 h light/dark cycle) with *ad libitum* access to standard laboratory chow and water. Animals were acclimatized for at least 7 days before experimentation. Euthanasia was performed by CO₂ inhalation in accordance with institutional and international ethical standards.

Isolation and preparation of IVC segments

Immediately after euthanasia, the abdominal cavity was opened via a midline incision. The IVC was carefully isolated, cleaned of surrounding connective tissue, and placed in ice-cold oxygenated Krebs–Henseleit solution. The Krebs–Henseleit solution contained the following (in mM): NaCl 118.0, KCl 4.7, CaCl₂ 2.5, KH₂PO₄ 1.2, MgSO₄ 1.2, NaHCO₃ 25.0, and glucose 11.0; pH 7.4. The vessel was cut into ring segments (3–4 mm in length) and prepared for functional studies.

Organ bath setup and equilibration

IVC rings were mounted between two stainless steel hooks in 10 mL organ bath chambers containing Krebs–Henseleit solution, continuously aerated with 95% O₂ and 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. An initial resting tension of 0.6 g was applied. Tissues were allowed to equilibrate for 60 min, during which the bath solution was replaced every 15–20 min. Experimental conditions were maintained constant throughout all recordings.

Experimental protocols and pharmacological interventions

After stabilization, the functional responses of the venous rings were assessed using a series of vasoconstrictor and vasodilator agents. The overall experimental workflow and pharmacological protocols used in this study are summarized schematically in Fig. 1. Following the 60-min equilibration period described above, endothelial integrity was evaluated before the initiation of pharmacological experiments. Endothelial integrity was assessed by phenylephrine (10⁻⁶ M)-induced contraction followed by methacholine (10⁻⁶ M)-induced relaxation. Only rings exhibiting > 70% relaxation to methacholine were considered endothelium-intact and included in subsequent experiments. For relaxation studies, IVC rings were precontracted with endothelin-1 (ET-1, 1 nM) until a stable plateau was achieved. This concentration was chosen based on preliminary experiments demonstrating stable, reproducible submaximal contractions. FTY720 was then administered cumulatively (1–30 μM) to generate concentration–response curves. The concentration range for FTY720 was selected based on previous vascular studies in arterial preparations (Tölle et al. 2005). Subsequent concentrations of FTY720 were added after stabilization of the preceding response to ensure reproducible cumulative concentration–response measurements. To investigate the underlying mechanisms, tissues were preincubated for 15–20 min with pharmacological inhibitors before FTY720 administration. Nitric oxide synthase was inhibited using N ω -nitro-L-arginine methyl ester (L-NAME, 100 μM), and soluble guanylate cyclase was inhibited using 1H-[1,2,4]oxadiazolo[4,3-a]quinoxalin-1-one (ODQ, 10 μM) to assess the involvement of the NO–cGMP signaling pathway. S1P receptor involvement was evaluated using the selective S1P₃ receptor antagonist CAY10444 (10 μM), applied before

Figure 1. Experimental protocol for vascular reactivity studies in the rat inferior vena cava.

FTY720 exposure. Inhibitor concentrations were selected based on previous studies demonstrating effective blockade in rat vascular tissues. FTY720 and CAY10444 were obtained from Cayman Chemical (Ann Arbor, MI, USA). ET-1, L-NAME, ODQ, phenylephrine hydrochloride, and methacholine chloride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Phenylephrine hydrochloride, methacholine chloride, L-NAME, and ET-1 were readily soluble in aqueous solution and were prepared directly in Krebs-Henseleit solution on the day of the experiment. FTY720 was initially dissolved in ethanol to prepare stock solutions and subsequently diluted in Krebs-Henseleit solution before application, with a final ethanol concentration not exceeding 0.05% (v/v). ODQ and CAY10444 were initially dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to prepare stock solutions and subsequently diluted in Krebs-Henseleit solution to achieve final concentrations of 10 μM, with the final DMSO concentration maintained below 0.1% (v/v). Vehicle control experiments were performed to confirm that the applied solvent concentrations did not affect vascular tone.

Recording of isometric tension

Isometric tension was continuously recorded using force transducers connected to a data acquisition system (LabChart, ADInstruments, Australia). Contractile responses to ET-1 were defined as 100%, and relaxation responses to FTY720 were expressed as the percentage decrease from precontracted tone. Concentration-response curves were constructed to determine maximal relaxation (*E*_{max}).

Isolated vessels were mounted in organ bath chambers containing Krebs solution and equilibrated for 60 min. Rings were precontracted with ET-1 (10⁻⁹ M), followed by

cumulative administration of FTY720 (1–30 μM). Mechanistic studies were performed in the presence of L-NAME (100 μM), ODQ (10 μM), or CAY10444 (10 μM).

Statistical analysis

Data are presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 9.0 (GraphPad Software, USA). Comparisons among multiple groups were performed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's or Bonferroni's post hoc test, as appropriate. Comparisons between two groups were performed using an unpaired Student's *t*-test. A value of *P* < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The number of independent experiments (*n*) is indicated in each figure legend.

Results

FTY720 induces concentration-dependent venorelaxation via the NO-cGMP pathway

In the first series of experiments, FTY720 induced a clear and reproducible concentration-dependent relaxation in inferior vena cava (IVC) rings precontracted with endothelin-1 (ET-1, 1 nM). The relaxation response increased progressively with cumulative concentrations of FTY720 (1–30 μM), reaching an *E*_{max} of 63.95 ± 5.1%, consistent with a pronounced venorelaxant effect (*P* < 0.001 vs. baseline). Representative traces are shown in Fig. 2, and the corresponding concentration-response curves are

Figure 2. Representative original traces showing vascular responses to cumulative FTY720 in the rat inferior vena cava. Vessels were precontracted with endothelin-1 (ET-1), followed by cumulative addition of FTY720 (1–30 μM). **A.** Control response showing concentration-dependent relaxation; **B.** ODQ (10 μM) attenuates relaxation, indicating involvement of soluble guanylate cyclase; **C.** L-NAME (100 μM) reduces relaxation, supporting nitric oxide synthase-dependent mechanisms.

presented in Fig. 3. These findings indicate that FTY720 exerts a direct venorelaxant effect in venous tissue under stable precontracted conditions. To investigate the underlying mechanisms, pharmacological inhibition of the nitric oxide (NO) pathway was performed. Preincubation with the nitric oxide synthase inhibitor L-NAME (100 μM) significantly reduced FTY720-induced relaxation compared with control conditions ($P < 0.001$), indicating a key role of endothelial NO production. Similarly, inhibition of soluble guanylate cyclase with ODQ (10 μM) significantly attenuated the relaxation response ($P < 0.001$), further supporting the contribution of the NO-cGMP pathway to FTY720-induced relaxation. In both conditions, the maximal relaxation response was significantly attenuated compared with FTY720 alone (Fig. 3; Table 1). Vehicle controls showed no significant relaxation. These results indicate that FTY720-induced venorelaxation is largely mediated via activation of the endothelial NO-cGMP signaling pathway.

Contribution of S1P₃ receptor signaling

To evaluate receptor-level mechanisms, the selective S1P₃ receptor antagonist CAY10444 (10 μM) was added before FTY720 treatment. Preincubation with CAY10444 significantly attenuated the venorelaxant response to FTY720, reducing relaxation to near-baseline levels (FTY720: $68.2 \pm 1.2\%$ vs. FTY720 + CAY10444: $1.2 \pm 0.6\%$, $P < 0.0001$; Fig. 4). The magnitude of inhibition observed with CAY10444 was comparable to that produced by L-NAME

Table 1. Maximal relaxation responses (E_{max} , %) induced by FTY720 in inferior vena cava rings precontracted with ET-1 (1 nM).

Pretreatment	pEC_{50}	E_{max} (%)
Control	4.76 ± 0.08	63.95 ± 5.1
ODQ 10 μM	$3.99 \pm 0.17^{***}$	$9.40 \pm 6.44^{***}$
L-NAME 100 μM	$3.05 \pm 0.35^{***}$	$16.01 \pm 4.01^{***}$

and ODQ, suggesting that S1P₃ receptor activation contributes to an upstream signaling mechanism associated with NO-cGMP-dependent relaxation. These results identify S1P₃ as the primary receptor subtype mediating the venorelaxant effect of FTY720 in the rat IVC.

Values represent maximal relaxation responses (E_{max}) and pEC_{50} obtained from the FTY720 cumulative concentration-response curves (10^{-6} to 3×10^{-5} M). Relaxation responses are expressed as a percentage (%) of the initial precontraction induced by ET-1. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM ($n = 5$). Statistical significance was assessed using two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's post hoc test. *** $P < 0.001$ indicates significant differences between inhibitor-treated groups (ODQ or L-NAME) and control.

Discussion

This study provides the first direct evidence that fingolimod (FTY720) induces significant relaxation in the rat inferior vena cava through a nitric oxide-dependent mechanism involving S1P₃ receptor activation. Attenuation of this response by L-NAME confirms a central role for eNOS, while

Figure 3. Effects of L-NAME and ODQ on FTY720-induced vasorelaxation in the rat inferior vena cava. Isolated rat inferior vena cava (IVC) rings were precontracted with ET-1 (1 nM), and cumulative concentration–response curves to FTY720 (10^{-6} to 3×10^{-5} M) were recorded under control conditions and in the presence of either L-NAME (100 μ M) or ODQ (10 μ M). FTY720 produced concentration-dependent relaxation under control conditions, whereas inhibition of nitric oxide synthase or soluble guanylate cyclase significantly attenuated the response. Relaxation is expressed as a percentage of ET-1-induced contraction. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM ($n = 5$ per group). *** $P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.05$.

inhibition by ODQ indicates involvement of downstream cGMP signaling. The near-complete abolition of the relaxation by the $S1P_3$ antagonist CAY10444 further identifies $S1P_3$ as the primary receptor subtype mediating this effect. Taken together, these findings indicate that FTY720-induced venorelaxation is predominantly mediated through activation of the endothelial NO–cGMP pathway.

These results are consistent with established sphingolipid signaling mechanisms, in which activation of $S1P$ receptors stimulates the PI3K/Akt pathway, leading to eNOS phosphorylation and enhanced NO production. This mechanism has been demonstrated in both endothelial models and isolated arterial vessel studies (Tölle et al. 2005). The present findings extend this well-characterized arterial mechanism to the venous system.

Importantly, sphingolipid signaling depends strongly on the distribution of $S1P$ receptor subtypes across vascular beds. Activation of $S1P_1$ and $S1P_3$ in endothelial cells promotes vasodilation through NO signaling, whereas $S1P_2$ and $S1P_3$ receptor activation in smooth muscle may induce vasoconstriction. These distinct signaling patterns underscore the importance of studying venous tissue directly rather than extrapolating from arterial data (Cantalupo et al. 2017).

The predominant role of $S1P_3$ in the present study is consistent with previous findings in rat arteries (Tölle et al. 2005) and suggests that $S1P_3$, rather than $S1P_1$, may be the primary endothelial receptor coupling to eNOS activation in response to FTY720 in this venous preparation. This is further supported by evidence that $S1P$ signaling contributes to endothelial barrier function (Tobia et al. 2012). The marked vasorelaxation observed in the present study suggests that endothelial signaling pathways play a major role. This observation is particularly relevant given the physiological role of large veins such as the inferior vena cava,

Figure 4. $S1P_3$ antagonism markedly attenuates FTY720-induced vasorelaxation in ET-1-precontracted rat inferior vena cava. Isolated inferior vena cava (IVC) rings were precontracted with endothelin-1 (ET-1, 1 nM) to establish a stable contractile tone. FTY720 ($-\log M = 4.5$, $\sim 30 \mu$ M; final bath concentration) induced marked vasorelaxation, expressed as the percentage of ET-1-induced contraction. This response was almost completely attenuated by preincubation with the selective $S1P_3$ antagonist CAY10444 (10 μ M), indicating a major contribution of $S1P_3$ -mediated signaling. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM ($n = 5$ per group). Statistical analysis was performed using an unpaired *t*-test. **** $P < 0.0001$ versus FTY720 alone.

which function as capacitance vessels that regulate venous return and cardiac preload (Rothe 1986; Gelman 2008).

The venorelaxant effects observed here may contribute to hemodynamic alterations associated with FTY720 therapy, including transient bradycardia and changes in blood pressure. NO appears to account for a major component of this effect, although not entirely. Residual relaxation suggests additional mechanisms, including prostaglandin pathways or potassium channel activation; these potential mechanisms remain speculative and require further investigation (Shishavan et al. 2016).

From a translational perspective, evidence from human studies supports the vascular effects of FTY720, indicating that sphingolipid signaling modulates endothelial function and vascular tone (Westhoff et al. 2007). The present findings suggest that venous modulation may contribute to these effects. Furthermore, FTY720 exerts anti-inflammatory and endothelial-protective effects, supporting a functional link between immune modulation and vascular regulation (Ahmed et al. 2019).

Although the present study demonstrates a clear venorelaxant effect of FTY720 in isolated vessels, previous *in vivo* studies have reported minimal sustained changes in systemic hemodynamics following FTY720 administration. For example, Tawadrous et al. (2002) showed that repeated oral administration up to 5 mg/kg/day did not significantly alter

renal, hepatic, or systemic blood flow. In contrast, acute intravenous administration at higher doses (1 mg/kg) produced only a transient increase in mean arterial pressure, which rapidly returned to baseline. Similarly, Zhao et al. (2017) reported that FTY720 (2.5 mg/kg) exerted antiplatelet and anticoagulant effects but did not reduce thrombus formation in inferior vena cava models, indicating limited efficacy in venous thrombosis despite measurable systemic effects.

This discrepancy between robust *ex vivo* venorelaxation and limited *in vivo* hemodynamic effects likely arises from several factors. First, the absence of compensatory autonomic and neurohormonal regulation in *ex vivo* preparations can unmask direct vascular effects that are buffered in intact organisms by baroreflexes and circulating vasoactive substances. Second, although the concentrations of FTY720 used in the present study exceed typical circulating levels reported *in vivo*, higher concentrations are commonly required in isolated vessel preparations to overcome diffusion barriers, lipophilic tissue sequestration, and the absence of systemic physiological amplification mechanisms. Accordingly, the concentration range of 1–30 μM was selected to define the direct vasoactive and mechanistic effects of FTY720 in venous tissue under controlled *ex vivo* conditions. Third, the venorelaxant action of FTY720 may become functionally relevant only under conditions of altered venous tone or during pathological states, such as heart failure or hypovolemia, where capacitance function is critical.

Limitations and future directions

This study has some limitations. First, the experiments were performed in isolated vessels under *in vitro* conditions, which do not fully reflect the complexity of *in vivo* hemodynamic and neurohormonal regulation. Second, circulating concentrations of FTY720 in humans and experimental animals are typically in the nanomolar range, whereas the micromolar concentrations used in this study should be interpreted as pharmacological. Such concentrations are commonly required in isolated vascular preparations to overcome diffusion limitations, lipophilic tissue partitioning, and reduced receptor accessibility. Third, the findings demonstrate a predominant role of the S1P_3 -NO-cGMP pathway; however, the potential roles of other S1P receptor subtypes and additional signaling mechanisms were not examined further, as the study focused on defining this primary pathway.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that fingolimod (FTY720) directly induces concentration-dependent relaxation in the rat inferior vena cava through a hierarchical signaling pathway involving S1P_3 receptor activation, endothelial nitric oxide release, and cGMP-mediated smooth muscle relaxation. These findings establish the S1P_3 -NO-cGMP axis as a central mechanism regulating venous tone and extend the pharmacological profile of FTY720 from the arterial

to the venous circulation. Given the central role of capacitance veins in regulating cardiac preload, S1P-mediated venorelaxation may contribute to the hemodynamic effects of FTY720 observed in clinical settings. Future studies in human venous tissue and *in vivo* models are needed to define the physiological relevance and therapeutic potential of targeting S1P signaling in venous function.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Animal experiments were conducted in accordance with applicable institutional and international guidelines and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, University of Prishtina (Approval No. 6804).

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

AD and HB supervised this research project, had full access to the study data, and were in charge; they also took responsibility for ensuring the integrity of the data. Study design: AD, AK. Instructions on the use of instruments for the outcome measures used in this study: AD. Analysis and interpretation of data: AD, HB, AK. Manuscript preparation: AD, AK, and SS. Statistical analysis: AD, AK. Critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content: AD, AK, HB, and SS. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text as well from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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